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Evolution of Water Masses in a Spin-Up Integration of an Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Global Circulation Model

by

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Abstract

This report describes a 60-yr spin-up experiment of a quasi-global version of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM). The meridional heat transport and overturning are illustrated and compared with observations and results of other numerical experiments. Maximum meridional heat transport occurs around 12°N with a value of about 1.5 PW in the global ocean and around 18°N with a value of 0.75 PW in the Atlantic Ocean. The model also captures the Global Conveyor Belt with the strength of 11 Sv around 56°N for the deep water cell. The processes which control the vertical mass transfer in the model, namely, detrainment, entrainment, diapycnal mixing and convection, are quantitatively investigated. It is found that detrainment, entrainment, and convection control the seasonal cycle of the mixed layer, whereas diapycnal mixing plays an important role in the deep part of the ocean and here it leads to ventilation of the bottom waters.

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1 Objective

This thesis investigates a 60-yr spin-up experiment with a quasi-global version of MICOM. Though we make a brief view of the behavior of the model, the main purpose of this study is to provide an investigation of the ventilation of the global ocean in the framework of an isopycnic coordinate model.

This thesis is organized as follows: In Sec. 2, an introduction to this study is given, and Sec. 3 offers a description of the model used in our experiment. The model implementation and spin-up integration are described in Sec. 4. In Sec. 5, we present some of the modelled fields, including derived quantities like ventilation of different layers caused by detrainment, entrainment, convection, and diapycnal mixing. Discussions of the subduction process, the mean features of the meridional overturning, and the conversion of surface to intermediate and deep water are also devoted to Sec. 5. Finally, we summarize our findings in Sec. 6.

2 Introduction

Ocean occupies three quarters of the earth surface. Because of its large heat capacity and because of its vast area, it plays an important role in the climate system of the earth. The coupled ocean-atmosphere system is, next after the solar heating of the Earth, the most important factor in the climate system. The atmosphere and the world ocean interact and seriously influence the weather and climate.

Because of the importance of the coupled ocean-atmosphere system, we must make efforts to understand their interaction and then predict their evolution. Numerical simulations may be the best choice to investigate the complicated ocean-atmosphere system. In the experiment presented here, we will focus the oceanic component of the climate system. To this end, a credible ocean general circulation model (OGCM) is needed.

Over the last three decades, several primitive equation OGCMs have been developed and the governing equations are commonly solved in a Cartesian framework in which fixed depths serves as vertical coordinate, and these models are often referenced as level models. The level models have a chronic deficiency to have either a weak meridional heat transport

or a thermocline that is too diffuse (Bryan, 1987). The models defects are believed to be associated with too strong mixing in the horizontal plane, whereas mixing and advection occur predominantly along isopycnals (planes of constant density with respect to a given reference pressure), or along neutral surfaces (i.e., locally defined isopycnal surfaces) in the interior ocean (McDougall, 1987). Therefore in regions of sloping isopycnals, spurious diapycnal buoyancy fluxes occur in level models due to horizontal mixing (Hu, 1997). In practice, iso-neutral mixing and advection are approximated in OGCMs by either use of an isopycnal diffusivity tensor (Redi, 1982) in level models, or use of isopycnal ocean models. In level models, use of a rotated local isopycnal diffusivity tends to mix along neutral surfaces, but advection still does not naturally occur along local isopycnal surfaces (Hu, 1997).

Based on the vertical density stratification of the ocean, isopycnic OGCMs are developed in which potential density serves as the vertical coordinate. In isopycnic models, both mixing and advection naturally occur along isopycnal surfaces. Isopycnic coordinate OGCMs have been developed in parallel by two groups: by the Max-Planck Institute at the University of Hamburg (Oberhuber, 1993) , and by Rosenstiel School of Marine and Atmospheric Sciences at the University of Miami (Bleck *et al.*, 1992). In our experiment, the Miami isopycnic-coordinate ocean model (MICOM) is used.

The isopycnic concept is appealing for several reasons (Drange, 1994): The preferred plane of advective flow in the ocean is along, rather than across, planes of constant density (Garçon *et al.*, 1993); the magnitude of the mixing is several orders of magnitude weaker in the diapycnal than in the isopycnal direction (Sarmiento *et al.*, 1976; Hoffert and Broecker, 1978; Sarmiento, 1980; Ledwell *et al.*, 1993; and Toole *et al.*, 1994), and this is embedded into the isopycnic concept per se; only two-dimensional prognostic equations have to be solved so there is no numerical smoothing of dynamic fields in the diapycnal direction, and the inclusion of a thermodynamic mixed layer represents a natural extension to the isopycnic concept.

One weakness of isopycnic models is that layers may disappear and reappear wherever and whenever called for by the dynamics, which puts severe constraints on the numerical treatment of layers and the actual solution techniques employed (Sun, 1993).

Another weakness is that the isopycnic coordinate models use a fixed reference pressure,

which in the case of a surface reference pressure means that the Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) is not recognized in the Atlantic Basin.

3 Description of MICOM

3.1 General description

MICOM, described in Bleck *et al.* (1992), is a primitive equation model. It uses Eulerian coordinates in the horizontal and potential density as a Lagrangian coordinate in the vertical. The model equations are spatially discretized on a C-grid in the horizontal plane (see appendix B) and is stepped forward in time with a split-explicit numerical scheme. The closure of prognostic variables is matched by means of a prognostic equation for the hydrostatic pressure balance in the vertical, a state equation that links temperature, salinity and potential density, and a turbulent kinetic closure equation for the upper mixed layer. In our experiment, MICOM has been configured with 21 layers (a bulk mixed layer on the top and 20 layers with prescribed and constant densities below) on a horizontal grid spanning the latitude range 90°S–72°N. The top mixed layer utilizes the Gaspar (1988) parameterization for dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy with the horizontal velocity vector, the layer thickness, temperature and salinity as prognostic variables; the 20 isopycnic layers have the horizontal velocity vector, the layer temperature and salinity as prognostic variables. The mixed layer is allowed to exchange mass with other isopycnic layers by detrainment and entrainment and its layer thickness is determined by the turbulent kinetic energy. A minimum mixed layer thickness is prescribed as 20 m in our experiment. At the ocean surface, the integral effect of wind stirring and buoyancy (heat and fresh water) fluxes are evaluated (see Sec. 3.5). The potential density of the layers in the dimensionless σ -units are: 23.54, 24.12, 24.70, 25.28, 25.77, 26.18, 26.52, 26.80, 27.03, 27.22, 27.38, 27.52, 27.61, 27.69, 27.74, 27.78, 27.82, 27.87, 27.91, 27.95, and 28.04 (see Fig. 1). The model equations are formulated on a spherical grid with a 3° latitude by 3° longitude mesh.

A validated thermodynamic-dynamic sea ice model was not available at the onset of this study, so the Arctic Ocean is not included in the model setup presented here. The presence of ice has been mimicked by setting the surface wind stirring and the heat fluxes

Figure 1: Potential densities of the isopycnic layers in the experiment (in σ -units).

to zero where the modeled mixed layer temperature or climatological Levitus sea surface temperature is below -1.8°C . No ice-related physical process, for instance, brine rejection (Anderson and Jones, 1991), is included in the simulation reported here.

Because of the coarse mesh of 3-by-3 degrees, we omit the Hudson bay, the Mediterranean sea, and the Barents Sea from the model domain. These areas are not expected to influence the model behavior to any great extent, although the outflow of saline Mediterranean Water may have some effect on the North Atlantic Ocean circulation (Reid, 1979, and Johnson, 1997).

3.2 Primitive equations involved in MICOM

The primitive equations involved in MICOM are the horizontal momentum equation, the mass continuity equation or the layer thickness tendency equation, and conservation equations for heat and salt. All of the equations are written in terms of a generalized vertical coordinate s (Bleck, 1978) to make them applicable to both interior isopycnic layers and

to the top mixed layer.

3.2.1 Momentum equation

The momentum equation reads:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + \nabla_s \frac{\vec{v}^2}{2} + (\zeta + f)\mathbf{k} \times \vec{v} + \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right) \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial p} + \nabla_\alpha M = -g \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial p} + \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right)^{-1} \nabla_s \left(\nu \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} \nabla_s \vec{v}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{v} = (u, v)$ is the horizontal velocity vector, p is the pressure, $\zeta = \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right)_s - \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)_s$ is the relative vorticity, f is the Coriolis parameter, $\vec{k}$ is the vertical unit vector, α is the specific volume, $M = gz + p\alpha$ is the Montgomery potential, gz is the geopotential, ν is the variable eddy viscosity coefficient, and finally, τ is the wind- and bottom-drag-induced shear-stress. Subscripts indicate which variable that is held constant during partial differentiation.

The expansion of the above vector equation has the following nonlinear form in x, y, s coordinates under adiabatic flow conditions (Bleck and Smith, 1990):

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{V^2}{2} - (\zeta + f)v = -\frac{\partial M}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\Delta p} [g \Delta \tau_x + \nabla \cdot (\nu \Delta p \nabla u)] \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \frac{V^2}{2} + (\zeta + f)u = -\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\Delta p} [g \Delta \tau_y + \nabla \cdot (\nu \Delta p \nabla v)] \quad (3)$$

where the second term on the right hand include the wind stress and the bottom related stress, and momentum diffusion.

3.2.2 Continuity equation

The continuity equation with s served as the vertical coordinate reads:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_s} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right) + \nabla_s \cdot \left(\vec{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

After integration over a coordinate layer bounded with two s surfaces s_{top} and s_{bot} , the continuity equation becomes a prognostic equation for the layer weight per unit area, $\Delta p = p_{bot} - p_{top}$ (Bleck *et al.*, 1992):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_s} \Delta p + \nabla_s \cdot (\vec{v} \Delta p) + \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right)_{bot} - \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s}\right)_{top} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Here $\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s}$ represents the vertical mass flux taken to be positive if in $+p$ (or downward) direction across an s surface.

Based on the knowledge that the layer thickness perturbation caused by barotropic flux divergence are proportional to the layer thickness itself, the pressure field is splitted into multiplicative factors (Bleck and Smith, 1990)

$$p = p'(1 + \eta) \quad (6)$$

where the dimensionless variable η , representing the barotropic component of the pressure field, is treated as depth-independent, while the baroclinic pressure field component p' has the property that its bottom value p'_b is time independent.

Follow Bleck and Smith (1990) and Bleck *et al.* (1992), the equation for baroclinic layer thickness tendency $\Delta p'$ has the following form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Delta p' + \nabla \cdot (V \Delta p') = \frac{\Delta p'}{p'_b} \nabla \cdot (\bar{v} p'_b) \quad (7)$$

where $V = \bar{v} + v'$ denotes the total velocity and $\bar{v}$ denotes the barotropic velocity. For subgrid-scale mixing term, the turbulent thickness diffusion term $\nabla \cdot (\overline{v' \Delta p'})$ is expressed in the form $-\nabla \cdot (\nu_1 \nabla \Delta p)$, where ν_1 denotes the thickness diffusivity. The flux corrected transport (FCT) scheme is employed for time integration of the above equation to exclude negative layer thickness (Zalesak, 1979; Smolarkiewicz and Clark, 1986).

3.2.3 Hydrostatic equation

Expressed in term of the Montgomery potential M , the hydrostatic equation becomes:

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial \alpha} = p \quad (8)$$

3.2.4 Heat and salt conservation equations

The conservation equation for temperature, salinity and buoyancy can be put in the following form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_s} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial s} T \right) + \nabla_s \cdot \left(\bar{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} T \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\dot{s} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} T \right) = \nabla_s \cdot \left(\nu_2 \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} \nabla_s T \right) + \kappa_T \quad (9)$$

Here T denotes any one of the thermodynamic variables (temperature, salinity, buoyancy), and κ_T represents the diabatic source of T .

In our experiment, wind-induced stress is assumed to be zero at the bottom of the mixed layer, which therefore is not permitted to be thinner than the Ekman layer. Bottom stress is distributed over the lowest 10 m of the water column and here it decreases linearly from $-\rho c_D |\vec{v}| \vec{v}$ to zero ($\vec{v}$ is the velocity vector over the lowest 10 cm). The no-slip boundary condition is applied in the present experiment.

Horizontal velocity and mass fields are staggered according to the so-called Arakawa C grid (see appendix B), which is not optimal for a coarse mesh (or non-eddy resolving) models (Arakawa and Lamb, 1977), including the present version of MICOM. Thermodynamic variables and $\vec{v}$ are treated as “layer” variables. This means that they are vertically uniform within layers and change discontinuously across the layer interfaces. Variables p, z and $\frac{\partial p}{\partial s}$ are defined as “level” variables, whereas M is a layer variable.

3.3 Boundary conditions

The numerical model formulation is completed by the specified boundary conditions and initial state. The solid boundary conditions for the ocean are insulating, impermeable, and no-slip or slip conditions. In MICOM, for slip condition:

$$\frac{\partial u_s}{\partial \pi} = 0 \quad (10)$$

and for no-slip condition:

$$u_s = 0 \quad (11)$$

here u_s denotes the tangential velocity to the boundary and π is the normal direction. Assuming the model domain is bounded by land to east, the following quantity is used to obtain an indication of the solid boundary at grid point (i, j, k) :

$$w_{i,j,k} = \max\{0, \min[1, \frac{p_{i,j,k+1} - p_{bi,j+1}}{\max(p_{i,j,k+1} - p_{i,j,k}, \epsilon_1)}]\} \quad (12)$$

Here ϵ_1 is a small positive number in order to prevent division by zero. There are three cases for $w_{i,j,k}$

Case A: $w_{i,j,k} = 1$, layer k intersects the boundary;

Case B: $w_{i,j,k} = 0$, layer k does not intersect the boundary;

Case C: $0 < w_{i,j,k} < 1$, part of layer k intersects the jump of the boundary existing between grid points (i, j) and $(i, j + 1)$

In MICOM, the variable *slip* is introduced to denote the option for the boundary condition:

a) $slip = 1$, slip boundary condition is chosen

b) $slip = -1$, no slip boundary condition is chosen

If a solid boundary is detected, an auxiliary velocity is introduced to express the behavior of the fluid around the immediate surroundings of the boundary:

$$u_{aux} = (1 - w_{i,j,k})u_{i,j,k} + w_{i,j,k}u_{i,j,k}slip \quad (13)$$

So we hold $u_{aux} = u_{i,j,k}$ for slip boundary condition and $u_{aux} = -u_{i,j,k}$ for no-slip boundary condition. In this experiment, the no-slip boundary condition is used.

At the sea surface, the boundary conditions for velocity, potential temperature, and salinity are respectively

$$A_{MV} \frac{\partial \vec{V}}{\partial z} = \tau \quad (14)$$

$$A_{HV} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\rho_0 C_w} Q^\theta \quad (15)$$

$$A_{HV} \frac{\partial S}{\partial z} = Q^S \quad (16)$$

where τ is the surface wind stress, Q^θ and Q^S are respectively the surface heat and salinity fluxes, C_w is the specific heat of sea water, and A_{MV} and A_{HV} are respectively the momentum vertical diffusivity and heat and salinity vertical diffusivity.

3.4 Mode splitting

In primitive equation OGCMs, the fast barotropic gravity waves generate a great constraint on the model integration time step. Various approaches have been developed to increase the model numerical efficiency. In the early stage of OGCMs, the barotropic waves were simply filtered out by either assuming that the deep ocean was at rest or by applying a rigid lid on the sea surface (as used by Bleck *et al.*, 1989, for instance). The rigid-lid method has

been widely used in the GFDL ocean model since its early development by Bryan (1969). In MICOM, the split-explicit scheme as described in Bleck and Smith (1990) is used to produce direct prediction of sea surface height; and consequently the possibility to compare simulated sea surface height with remotely sensed radar altimetry data.

Integration of split-explicit scheme is also faster than the rigid-lid scheme (Bleck *et al.*, 1992). The split-explicit scheme used in MICOM separately calculates the barotropic and baroclinic components of prognostic variables. The barotropic components are calculated every time step, whereas the baroclinic components are calculated every 16 barotropic timesteps.

3.5 Exchange between atmosphere and ocean

The atmospheric fields that force the ocean mixed layer include buoyant (thermal and fresh water) and dynamic forcings. In MICOM, the thermal forcing consists of the net solar radiation, the net longwave radiation, and the turbulent sensible and latent heat fluxes at the air-sea interface. The dynamic forcing is mainly the wind stress. The thermal balance at the air-sea interface may therefore be expressed as

$$B = R + SH + LH \quad (17)$$

where B is the heat balance at the air-sea interface, R is the radiative transfer between the ocean and atmosphere (radiative forcing to the sea surface), SH is the turbulent sensible heat flux caused by temperature difference between air and sea surface, LH is the turbulent latent heat flux caused by evaporation of water at the sea surface. If B is positive, the oceans lose heat to the atmosphere, the sea surface temperature will decrease and the thickness of ocean mixed layer will tend to increase. If the sea surface temperature is lower than the freezing point, sea ice is formed. This situation mainly takes place in winter and subpolar oceans.

Once sea ice is formed (in the present version of MICOM, sea ice formation is mimicked when the sea surface temperature is below -1.8°C), based on the fact that the sea ice acts as the obstacle to the air-sea exchange and the high albedo of sea ice, the thermal net balance at the air-sea interface is set to zero in the model.

In the present version of MICOM, the turbulent sensible heat flux is parameterized by a very simple formula; taking the turbulent heat transfer coefficient as constant (in fact, it depends on the wind velocity and sea state):

$$H = C(T_{sea} - T_{air}) \quad (18)$$

where C is a constant heat transfer coefficient, T_{sea} is the sea surface temperature, T_{air} is the air temperature (in practice, taking the air temperature at the height of 2 m above the sea surface). The turbulent latent heat flux is parameterized by the following equation

$$\varepsilon = C * L(q_{sea} - q_{air}) \quad (19)$$

where C is the same constant heat transfer coefficient as that used in the calculation of sensible heat flux (indeed, they are different), L is the latent heat of evaporation, q_{air} is the specific humidity of air, q_{sea} is the saturated specific humidity at the sea surface temperature.

The net fresh water forcing of atmosphere on the ocean is evaporation and precipitation, which influence the sea surface salinity, and therefore influence the sea surface density and consequently the buoyancy flux. In the model, the numerical equation of state is used to determine the density variation which is based on the variation in both salinity and temperature. The freshwater forcing is set to zero if sea ice is present.

The dynamic forcing of the atmosphere on the ocean is mainly the wind stress which in common conditions transfer momentum into the ocean. The surface wind stress can be easily expressed by using the bulk transfer method:

$$\tau = \rho_a C_D |\vec{U}| \vec{U} \quad (20)$$

where C_D denotes the drag coefficient, and $\vec{U}$ wind velocity. The friction velocity u_* is obtained by the following expression:

$$u_*^2 \vec{X} = \frac{\tau_s}{\rho_0} \quad (21)$$

Here $\vec{X}$ is the horizontal unit vector, τ_s is the surface wind stress.

3.6 Parameterization of ocean mixed layer

In both the ocean and atmosphere systems, the wind shear always acts as a source of turbulence and the buoyancy may act as a source or sink of turbulence. In MICOM, there are two options for the parameterization of ocean mixed layer: the parameterization of Kraus and Turner (1967), and of Gaspar (1988). In our experiment, the Gaspar type for turbulence closure is adopted. If the turbulent kinetic energy is positive, which means that generation of turbulence caused by wind stress dominates over the buoyancy flux and dissipation, entrainment will occur, and the opposite situation holds for detrainment. The mixed layer is assumed to be vertically homogeneous. During the entrainment process, the excess of turbulent kinetic energy is balanced by mixing the water masses from the layers below into the mixed layer, whereas the deficit of turbulent kinetic energy is compensated by passing parts of the mixed layer water to the sub-surface layers. Readers interested in the detailed algorithms for entrainment and detrainment are referred to Bleck *et al.* (1992) and User's Manual of MICOM (Langlois *et al.*, 1997).

3.7 Parameters' list

For given boundary conditions and realistic topography, the solutions of global isopycnic model described previously are controlled by the parameters: the bottom drag coefficient c_D , the momentum diffusivity velocity ν , the thickness diffusivity velocity ν_1 , and the temperature and salinity diffusivity velocity ν_2 . The values used in our experiment are:

the dimensionless bottom drag coefficient: $c_D = 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$

diffusion velocity for momentum mixing: $\nu = 2.0$ (cm/s)

diffusion velocity for thickness diffusion: $\nu_1 = 1.0$ (cm/s)

diffusion velocity for temp/saln. mixing: $\nu_2 = 1.0$ (cm/s)

In addition, it should be mentioned that the diapycnic mixing routine for computational reason is called every 30 baroclinic time steps.

4 Model implementation and spin-up

The model is started from rest, and initialized from the September Levitus and Boyer (1994) and Levitus *et al.* (1994) datasets, when the mixed layer at high northern latitudes is at its shallowest. In order to use the initial fields, convective adjustments of all vertical instabilities are necessary. The adjustment is done by repartitioning the temperature and salinity profiles between neighboring pairs of levels and at the same time maintaining the total amount of heat and salt in any grid column. The depths of the isopycnic interfaces, and the temperature and salinity of the layers, were then calculated by assuming a linear trend for temperature and salinity between each standard depth at which data is held in the Levitus dataset. The initial density and depth of the mixed layer vary in space, and therefore differ from the experiment of New *et al.* (1995), in which the initial mixed layer is given a uniform depth of 50 m and a uniform density of $\sigma = 25.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. A realistic bottom topography is used. The surface forcing functions applied to the model includes the Hellerman and Rosenstein (1983) winds, and the Esbensen and Kushnir (1981) heat fluxes. These climatological data sets have a coarse horizontal mesh, with grid points every 2° or 3° latitude and longitude, and contain a seasonal cycle, with one data set for each month, but do not change year to year through the model integration (climatological forcing).

At each model grid point and at each time step, linear interpolation in time was used to calculate the appropriate values from the monthly forcing datasets. The heat fluxes applied to the model mixed layer were the sum of the value (which is derived from the monthly datasets linearly) and a restoring term, which provided a partial relaxation (with approximately a 4-month time scale for a 100m thick water column) of the mixed layer temperature and salinity to Levitus climatology (New *et al.*, 1995). The heat flux applied in the model can then be expressed by the following expression (counted positive into the ocean):

$$Q_{app} = Q_{obs} + \lambda(T_{lev} - T_{mod}) \quad (22)$$

where Q_{obs} is the observed heat flux linearly derived from the monthly dataset, $\lambda = 35 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W cm}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, T_{lev} is the Levitus surface temperature, and T_{mod} is the model produced mixed layer temperature. A corresponding expression was employed for the freshwater flux

with the same relaxation time scale. In the ocean interior, there is no relaxation employed in any way. Since relaxation of wind stress is not used, Ekman pumping and the momentum transfer from the atmosphere to the ocean are independent of the model state, and the identical year by year throughout the spin-up integration.

Diapycnic mixing between the interior layers, including both the cabelling process and turbulent diffusion, is present in our experiment. This is different from the Bleck *et al.* (1992) and New *et al.* (1995) studies which only include the cabelling process. In our experiment, water mass are able to pass between the mixed layer and the interior layers in the seasonal cycle of entrainment and detrainment, and to pass between interior layers by diapycnic mixing. In addition, convective mixing is also included in the study presented here.

We spin up the model for 60 years. The baroclinic time step used in the spin-up is 2400 s. In the following, we focus on the last 40 years of the spin-up integration.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Annually zonally averaged temperature and salinity in the global ocean

As we can see in Fig. 2 there is a broad warm tongue near 15° at the surface in both hemispheres, which is related to the Ekman convergence and downwelling between trade wind zone and mid-latitude westerlies. Similarly, the relatively cold water in the tropics is caused by Ekman divergence and upwelling. From Figs. 2 and 3 we can see that the warm tongues in both hemispheres are also salty, and this feature is associated with the excess evaporation over precipitation in the subtropical areas (Peixoto and Oort, 1992). The warm and salty togues penetrate to layer 5 (potential density 25.77) around 30°N and 30°S respectively. From the left lower part of the figures, we can also see the influence of the fresh and cold Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW).

Figure 2: Annually zonally averaged temperature of model year 50.

5.2 Annually averaged mixed layer temperature and salinity fields in the global ocean

Figs. 4 and 5 show the mixed layer temperature and salinity fields in global ocean in model year 50. The mixed layer temperature reaches its highest value in the tropical west Pacific. In the tropics and the subtropics, temperatures in the west of the individual ocean basins are higher than those in the east, and the opposite situation holds for the high latitudes. This is mainly caused by the warm polarward currents (for instance, the Gulf Stream, and Kuroshio Current) and the cold equatorward currents (for instance, the California Current). The low temperatures in the equatorial eastern parts of the Pacific and Atlantic Basins are caused by Ekman divergence and therefore upwelling of colder sub-surface waters (Drange, 1996). The temperature field is basically zonal and decreases from subtropical to high latitudes (net gain of radiative flux is negative at high latitudes). Compared with the climatological dataset of surface temperature (Levitus and Boyer, 1994), the surface ocean is warmer, especially in the west equatorial areas of the three individual basins (

Figure 3: Annually zonally averaged salinity of model year 50.

about 2°C higher in the Indian Ocean, and about 1°C higher in the Atlantic Ocean). This feature, together with too strong upwelling in the eastern parts of the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, are probably related to the coarse horizontal resolution of the model.

Fig. 5 shows that the Atlantic Ocean is more saline than the Pacific Ocean, and that the Pacific Ocean is more saline than the India Ocean. These features are due to the distribution of the excess evaporation over precipitation (Peixoto and Oort, 1992). The maximum salinity in the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans locate in the subtropical areas, which is in accordance with the higher evaporation in these areas. The minimum salinity are found at high latitudes and near equator, which are related to the fresh water runoff and the net precipitation (Intertropical Convergence Zone in the atmosphere), respectively.

The annual averaged density distribution is displayed in Fig. 6. The low density in the equatorial areas is caused by the effects of both high temperature and low salinity waters encountered here. Figs. 7 and 8 show the annual mean atmospheric wind stress applied to the model and the mixed layer velocity field. The model captures the main large-scale sea currents of the real ocean. From the figure, we can recognize the North Equatorial

Figure 4: Annually averaged surface temperature of model year 50.

Figure 5: Annually averaged surface salinity of model year 50.

Figure 6: Annually averaged density distribution of mixed layer of model year 50 in σ_0 -unit.

Current, South Equatorial Current, Antarctic Circumpolar Current, the Kuroshio Current in the Pacific Ocean, and the Gulf Stream in the Atlantic Ocean. Because of the absence of the Arctic Ocean, the Drake Passage is the only channel of direct exchange between the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans. Between the Indian Ocean and the Atlantic Ocean, the Agulhas Current shows up as a current pathway in the opposite direction to the Antarctic Circumpolar Current.

With the combination of Figs. 4 and 8, we can expect that the mixed layer warm currents transport heat from the Pacific to the Indian Ocean (via the archipelago between Thailand and Australia), then to the Atlantic Ocean (via the Agulhas Current). The surface sea currents are heavily influenced by the momentum transferred from the atmosphere, which is transported vertically into the water until the strong stratification below the ocean mixed layer prevents its further penetration. Thus, the sea surface currents show the pattern of the atmospheric wind field, and consequently with the atmospheric pressure field on the sea surface (mid and high latitudes). There are atmospheric subtropical high pressure systems in both hemispheres (especially strong in the Northern Hemisphere), where the

Figure 7: Annually averaged surface wind stress applied to the model.

Figure 8: Annually averaged sea currents of model year 50.

atmospheric boundary layer is divergent and the curl of wind stress is negative, therefore the ocean turbulent mixed layer is forced to be convergent, leading to downward Ekman pumping and positive sea surface elevation (see Figs. 9 and 10). The negative sea surface elevation associated with the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) in Fig. 10 is related to the atmospheric low pressure field. Under the forcing of this low pressure system, the wind induced Ekman transports give rise to divergence of the surface waters (positive Ekman pumping, see Fig. 9) which facilitates upwelling of sub-surface water. This upwelling is perhaps the single most important oceanographic process of Antarctic waters (Foldvik and Gammelsrød, 1988). The negative sea surface elevation along the coastline is induced by the off-shore Ekman transport.

In the North Atlantic Ocean, the annually averaged downward Ekman pumping velocity falls in the range of 20-60 m yr⁻¹ in the subtropical gyre (see Fig. 9), which is consistent with the result of Marshall (1993).

5.3 Ventilation of the ocean interior

Figure 11 shows the temporal evolution of the global-averaged layer thickness anomalies (layer index increases from left to right, and from top to bottom). This is the natural way to view water mass changes in an isopycnic model and illustrates the changes in the volume of water masses confined to a specific density intervals. The mixed layer has a pronounced seasonal cycle (Levitus, 1982; New *et al.*, 1995, Drange, 1996), but here we focus on the yearly variation of the layers. On the time scales considered here, large volume changes are captured in the layers with potential density varying from 27.03 (layer 9) to 27.74 (layer 15), and from 27.87 (layer 18) to 27.91 (layer 19).

During the integration from year 30 to 60, layers 2-6 (potential densities 24.12, 24.70, 25.28, 25.77 and 26.18) are essentially inactive in the water mass transfer. However, the layers with potential densities ranging from 27.52 (layer 12) to 27.74 (layer 15) show clear gain of water. The density of layer 15 is close to that of the water mass that is thought to be formed in Labrador Sea area (27.75) (McCartney and Talley, 1982). According to the model, the densest mixed layer waters occur in the GIN basin, and in the Labrador basin (see Fig. 47) and here the mixed layer reaches a depth of about 1400m in March of year

Figure 9: Annually averaged Ekman pumping (m yr^{-1}) deduced from the wind stress applied to the model (contour interval is 20 m yr^{-1}).

Figure 10: Annually averaged sea surface elevation of model year 50 (unit: cm.).

Figure 11: Layer thickness anomalies for the global ocean, layer index increases from left to right and from top to bottom.

50 (Fig. 48).

The density of the water in these regions match that of layer 15 and 16, and since the model can not support hydrostatic instability, convection will occur and water is entrained into layers of 15 and 16. The layers with density 28.04 (layer 21) shows no obvious variation in the model although this water mass match the density of the overflow water from the GIN Seas (McCartney and Talley, 1982 and Dickson *et al.*, 1990). It should be noted that in our experiment, the Labrador Sea and the GIN Seas are the only possible sources of the deep water formation in March (see Fig. 47). In addition, the density of the mixed layer in Southern Hemisphere reaches its maximum value of 27.5 in the Weddell Sea in September, so this is also a source of renewal of deep water in our experiment (see Fig. 12).

Figure 13 shows the long-term layer thickness anomalies in the Atlantic Ocean. From this

Figure 12: Mixed layer density in September of model year 50.

figure, the deep water water formation is more obvious than in Fig. 11. Note the different scales for layers of 13-16, 18 and 19. Among these layers, layer 13 (potential density 27.61) entrains the largest amount of water from other layers during the integration. Similarly, layer 18 (potential density 27.87) and layer 19 (potential density 27.91) lose the largest amount of water. This lose is mainly due to diapycnal mixing as will be discussed in

Figure 13: Layer thickness anomalies for the Atlantic Ocean, layer index increases from left to right and from top to bottom.

Sec. 5.8. Note that layers 2-5 are inactive in the ventilation of the Atlantic Ocean.

By comparing Figs. 11 and 13, we find that layers of 12-15 (potential density ranging from 27.52 to 27.74) increase their volume almost linearly in time during years 40-60, while layers 18 and 19 lose water linearly in time. The rates of variation in water masses of these layers in the Atlantic Ocean and the global ocean are listed in Tabs. 1 and 2, respectively (the rates are derived by using a least-squares algorithm).

Based on the model grid used here, the areas of the global ocean and the Atlantic Ocean

	layer12	layer13	layer14	layer15	layer18	layer19
rate of variation(m yr ⁻¹)	+0.8	+2.3	+1.8	+1.4	-3.2	-3.1

Table 1: Basin averaged change in thickness of layers 12-15, 18 and 19 in the Atlantic Ocean for model years 40 to 60.

	layer12	layer13	layer14	layer15	layer18	layer19
rate of variation(m yr ⁻¹)	+0.8	+0.8	+0.7	+0.5	-1.0	-0.9

Table 2: Basin averaged thickness of layers 12-15, 18 and 19 in the global ocean for model years 40 to 60.

are about $3.46 \times 10^8 \text{ km}^2$ and $0.92 \times 10^8 \text{ km}^2$ respectively, giving a ratio between the area of the global ocean and that of the Atlantic Ocean of about 3.7. From the data in Tabs. 1 and 2, we conclude that the variation of the deep ocean water masses in the model is mainly taking place in the Atlantic Ocean, especially in layers 15, 18 and 19 with potential densities of 27.74, 27.87 and 27.91, respectively. It should be mentioned that ventilation of layer 12 also takes place in the Southern Ocean.

Figure 14 illustrates vertical sections of the isopycnals through 36°W in the Atlantic Ocean. In the North Atlantic, the mixed layer descends to about 500 m near 40°N and 1000 m near 57°N in March of year 20. The layers below layer 12 (potential density 27.52) do not outcrop into the mixed layer and the thickness of layer 13 (potential density 27.61) is

relatively thin. In year 50, the mixed layer reaches the depth of about 1400 m near 60°N. It is seen that layer 13 has thickened considerably, and that it outcrops into the mixed layer near 57°N. This is because the mixed layer density at this position and time is close to 27.61 (Figs. 47 and 48), so water is entrained into layer 13. In the South Atlantic (see Fig. 25), the mixed layer reaches the depth of about 200 m near 60°S in March of both year 20 and year 50, and reaches a depth of about 600 m near 66°S in September, and leading to entrainment of mixed layer water into layer 12 (potential density 27.52).

Figure 15 shows vertical sections of isopycnals through 168°E in the Pacific Ocean. In the North Pacific, the mixed layer arrives to the maximum depth of about 400 m near 36°N and at this position layer 6 (potential density 26.18) outcrops into the mixed layer in March of both year 20 and year 50. Compared with Fig. 14, the isopycnals in the deep Pacific Ocean are situated deeper than those in the Atlantic Ocean because the different T,S profiles in the two basins (see Figure. 16).

5.4 Meridional heat transport in the global ocean and Atlantic Ocean

The annually averaged meridional heat transport in the global ocean (calculated from the modelled temperature and volume transport) is shown in Fig. 17. The zonally averaged heat flux Q is given by:

$$Q = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-H}^{\eta} \rho C_p v \theta dz d\lambda \quad (23)$$

where H is the ocean depth, η is the sea surface elevation, ρ is the density of sea water, C_p is the specific heat of sea water, v is the meridional velocity component, θ is potential temperature, z is depth (negative downward), and λ is longitude. In the calculation, we employ the Boussinesq approximation (Gill, 1982) and we use the following differential form of the above equation:

$$Q = 0.5 \sum \sum \rho_0 C_p v(i, j) (\theta(i, j - 1) + \theta(i, j)) ds dz \quad (24)$$

here i, j denote the grid indexes in the zonal and meridional directions, respectively; ds is the zonal grid-distance and dz is the layer thickness (note the staggered Arakawa C grid, see appendix B).

Figure 14: Isopycnals through 36°W (the Atlantic Ocean) in March of years 20 (upper panel) and 50 (lower panel). The bold lines show the interfaces of layers 14-15 and 15-16.

Figure 15: Isopycnals through 168°E (the Pacific Ocean) in March of years 20 (upper panel) and 50 (lower panel). The bold lines show the interfaces of layers 14-15 and 15-16.

Figure 16: Annually averaged temperature and salinity profiles at the position of 39°N, 36°W (Atlantic Ocean, upper panel) and 36°N, 168°E (Pacific Ocean, lower panel) in year 50. Solid line denotes temperature, while dashed line denotes salinity.

Figure 17: Meridional heat transport in the global ocean in year 50.

Figure 18: Annually meridional heat transport in the Atlantic Ocean in year 50.

According to Fig. 17, maximum northward heatflux of 1.5 PW is reached in year 50 around 12°N. In the Southern Hemisphere, maximum southward heatflux of 1.7 PW is found in year 50 around 18°S. In the Northern Hemisphere, the heatflux has a rapid decrease between 18°N and 42°N, whereas in Southern Hemisphere, the southward heat transport decreases abruptly between 24°S and 48°S. As we know, both of the ocean and atmosphere transport heat from the subtropics to polar regions as a result of balancing the global energy budget (Peixoto and Oort, 1992), and it is the meridional heat transport that keeps polar regions warmer than they otherwise would be. The estimates of this annual mean meridional heat transport for both ocean and atmosphere are about 4 PW and 3.2 PW, respectively (Hartman, 1994). These estimates were made by applying energy balance at the top of the atmosphere (planetary energy balance), and the oceanic heat transport is then taking as a residual term. However, the estimates made by applying energy balance at the surface of the ocean are considerably less than that made by applying the energy balance at the top of atmosphere. The result of our experiment is in agreement with the estimates obtained by applying the energy balance at the sea surface, which is about 1.6 PW around 25°N (Hsiung, 1985, and Hartman, 1994). Compared with other results of numerical experiments, the maximum northward heat transport is 0.28 PW higher than Hu's (1997) result and 0.4 PW higher than the reported value of Danabasoglu and McWilliams (1995), and 0.1 PW higher than Bleck's result (Bleck *et al.*, 1996) which is obtained by using MICOM with a resolution of 1.4°-by-1.4°.

If we apply energy balance to the sea surface, we get the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial E_s}{\partial t} = R_s - LH - SH - F_o \quad (25)$$

where $\frac{\partial E_s}{\partial t}$ represents the local storage of energy in the surface which is important for the seasonal cycle in the ocean and the diurnal cycle over land, R_s is the net radiative heating (including both net solar heating and longwave cooling) of the surface, LH is the latent heat from the ocean surface to the atmosphere, SH is the sensible heat from the ocean to the surface, and F_o is the heat transport of the ocean. For the stationary case, and assuming that the local storage is small, the energy balance can be rewritten as:

$$R_s - LH - SH = F_o \quad (26)$$

In this case, the horizontal heat transport equals the thermal forcing of the surface which might be expected for the annual cycle of the ocean or the diurnal cycle over land. Therefore, the thermal forcing of the surface or the heat transfer between the ocean and atmosphere play an important role in the behavior of the OGCMs.

Figure 18 shows the zonally and annually averaged heat transport in the Atlantic Ocean. Maximum northward heat transport of 0.75 PW is found around 18°N with a rapid decrease between 18°N and 42°N due to the loss of heat from the Gulf Stream. According to the estimate made by Hall and Bryden (1982), the northward maximum heat transport in Atlantic Ocean at 25°N is 1.2 PW, which is 60 percent larger than our model result. Our result is also different from that of New *et al.* (1995), using an Atlantic Ocean only version of MICOM, in which the maximum heat transport was about 0.67 PW around 24°N. This maximum northward heat flux is caused by the warm wind-driven tropical water associated with the Gulf Stream. The result is in good agreement with Hu's value of 0.75 PW (Hu, 1997), but smaller than Bleck's value of 0.9 PW (Bleck *et al.*, 1996). The result of the model also indicates that the Atlantic Ocean transports heat northward across equator.

5.5 Meridional cross-section from the individual basins

Figures 19 and 20 show the annually-averaged meridional cross-section of potential temperature and salinity in the Atlantic Ocean along 24°W in model year 50. In the Southern Oceans, a fresh and cold tongue, which represents the mixture of AABW and AAIW in MICOM, extends to the Southern Ocean. In the North Atlantic Ocean, the model captures a warm and saline tongue extending to 12°S with the characteristic salinity of 34.9 psu. In addition, the northward tongue overlies the southward due to the salinity difference in the model.

Figures 21 and 22 show the annually-averaged meridional cross-section of temperature and salinity in the Pacific Ocean along 168°E in model year 50. In the Pacific Ocean, the southward fresh tongue overlies the northward due to the salinity difference.

Figure 19: Annually averaged meridional cross-section of temperature in model year 50 along 24°W in the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 20: Annually averaged meridional cross-section of salinity in model year 50 along 24°W in the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 21: Annually averaged meridional cross-section of temperature in model year 50 along 168°E in the Pacific Ocean.

Figure 22: Annually averaged meridional cross-section of salinity in model year 50 along 168°E in the Pacific Ocean.

5.6 Zonal cross-section through subtropical gyres in the Northern Hemisphere

Figures 23 and 24 show the zonal sections of both salinity and temperature along 24°N. Water in the west Pacific Ocean is warmer than in the east Pacific Ocean due to the upwelling of sub-surface water in the east. In Northern Hemisphere, within the same lower isopycnals, the Atlantic Ocean is warmer and more saline than the Pacific Ocean, whereas in the Southern Hemisphere, the Atlantic Ocean almost has the same temperature and salinity as the Pacific Ocean within the same lower isopycnals.

5.7 Mixed layer thickness

The mixed layer thickness shows a profound seasonal cycle over the global ocean (see Fig. 25). Because of heating or cooling, the mixed layer gets deeper in winter and shallower in summer in both hemispheres. In the world oceans, the deepest mixed layer in the simulation occurs in the Labrador and GIN basins in March due to both the convection and entrainment, while in Southern hemisphere the mixed layer reaches the deepest state in September.

The mixed layer deepening in the Labrador Sea and GIN Basins is about 600 m from January to March, and about 1450 m in March. McCartney and Talley (1982) reveal a large area covering most of the Labrador Sea and with a tongue extending to the Irminger basin where the mixed layer reaches the depth over 1000 m, in qualitative agreement with the model.

The mixed layer deepens along and just north of a line stretching from about 25°N of the North American Continent to about 45°N of the European Continent where the north-eastern portions of the outcropping isopycnals are gradually entrained into the mixed layer (Drange, 1994) (also see Figs. 14 and 47). By year 50, the mixed layer thickness in March is consistent with the observations of Levitus (1982), in which a band of relatively deep mixing stretches across the central North Atlantic Ocean and reaches depths between 250 m and 500 m. McCartney and Talley (1982) indicate a similar region with a mixed

Figure 23: Zonal cross-section of salinity in January of model year 50 along 24°N.

Figure 24: Zonal cross-section of temperature in January of model year 50 along 24°N.

Figure 25: Seasonal cycle of mixed layer thickness for (from above) January, March, July and October in model year 50.

layer thickness up to 400 m. In the North Pacific Ocean, the mixed layer deepens around 36°N , 162°E and reaches a depth of about 350 m in March (also see Figs 15 and 47). In the Southern Hemisphere, the largest variation of mixed layer thickness occurs along the Antarctic Circumpolar Current.

In MICOM, the vertical mass exchange is controlled by three processes: the mixed layer entrainment and detrainment; convection; and diapycnal mixing in the ocean interior. It is mainly entrainment and detrainment (also convection at high latitudes) that maintain the seasonal cycle of the mixed layer thickness in MICOM.

As shown in Fig. 26, for January, the mixed layer detrainment mainly happens in the Southern Ocean and the maximum values locate near the Weddell Sea and around 21°E , 53°S . In the Northern Hemisphere, the entrainment occurs in both the North Pacific and the North Atlantic Oceans. In the North Pacific Ocean, the maximum entrainment is found around 42°N , 180°E with a value of about 150 m, while in the North Atlantic Ocean, entrainment is found near Irminger Basin and GIN Seas, and north of the 25°N – 45°N line. Hence, in January entrainment is the dominant process in the Northern Hemisphere to deepen the mixed layer.

In March, detrainment mainly happens in the mid-latitude oceans in the Northern Hemisphere (Fig. 27). In the North Pacific Ocean, maximum detrainment occurs around 36°N , 186°E with a value of about 150 m, while in the North Atlantic Ocean, it occurs around the 25°N – 45°N line. Therefore, in March, the mixed layer detrainment begins to ventilate the subtropic gyres in both the North Pacific and the North Atlantic Oceans, and the mixed layer at mid-latitude begins to retreat. In the subpolar ocean, mainly in the Labrador and Irminger Basins, both convection and entrainment still deepen the mixed layer, so the entrainment process is dominant.

In April (Fig. 28), the mixed layer in the Southern Ocean deepens by entrainment. The detrainment at mid-latitude of the North Pacific and North Atlantic Oceans is stronger than in March, and continue to pass water masses to the thermocline and ventilating the subtropical gyres. In the North Atlantic Ocean, the ventilation of the subtropical gyre is along and north of the 25°N – 45°N line, whereas in the North Pacific Ocean this ventilation is along a belt around 30°N . In addition, detrainment at high latitudes begins to ventilate the subpolar oceans. Maximum detrainment occurs in the Irminger and Labrador Basins

Figure 26: Mixed layer convection (upper panel), detrainment (mid-panel) and entrainment (lower panel) in January of model year 50.

Figure 27: Mixed layer convection (upper panel), detrainment (mid-panel) and entrainment (lower panel) in March of model year 50.

Figure 28: Mixed layer convection (upper panel), detrainment (mid-panel) and entrainment (lower panel) in April of model year 50.

and here it reaches about 1400 m. The mixed layer begins the retreat at high latitudes by this detrainment.

In July (Fig. 29), the mixed layer is still in the retreat phase governed by detrainment in the Northern Hemisphere, whereas the mixed layer in the Southern Ocean is in the deepening phase caused by entrainment. Note that maximum convection and detrainment reach about 3200 m at equator near 228°E. At this point, the convection penetrates into the deep ocean and detrains a large amount of water to the sub-surface layers. It is believed that this vertical mixing is caused by improper equatorial dynamics in the model.

In September (Fig. 30), the mixed layer depth in the Northern Hemisphere is at its minimum. In the Southern Hemisphere, the mixed layer begins to retreat by detrainment. Maximum convection and detrainment reaches above 3300 m near 21°E, 42°S.

5.8 Vertical mass transfer due to different processes

We have monitored the monthly detrainment, entrainment, diapycnal and convective fluxes between the mixed layer and all of the isopycnals in model year 50 (Tab. 3), but we did not detect detrainment in layer 18 (potential density 27.87) or layer 19 (potential density 27.91), nor did we detect convection to these layers throughout the year. The entrainment from layers 18 and 19 to the mixed layer only happens in March and April of model year 50. This is one of the reasons why layer 18 always loses water during the spin-up integration. Figure 31 shows the mixed layer entrainment from layer 18 in March of model year 50. As shown in this figure, the entrainment of layer 18 is mainly confined to GIN Seas and the maximum entrainment reaches a value of about 70 m in March. The entrainment of layer 19 is also mainly confined to GIN Seas and the maximum value reaches about 10 m in March.

Figure 32 shows the water transfer of layer 19 with other isopycnals by diapycnal mixing in model year 50. In the Southern Ocean and over a large part of the Atlantic Ocean, layer 19 loses water by diapycnal mixing through the year. As mentioned in Tab. 2, layer 19 loses water at the rate of 0.9 m yr⁻¹ during model year 40 to 60. We checked the mass transfer of layer 19 in the whole year and found that the mass reduction rate of layer 19 is 0.01 m yr⁻¹ due to entrainment and is 0.89 m yr⁻¹ due to diapycnal mixing (Tabs. 3). We

Figure 29: Mixed layer convection (upper panel), detrainment (mid-panel) and entrainment (lower panel) in July of model year 50.

Figure 30: Mixed layer convection (upper panel), detrainment (mid-panel) and entrainment (lower panel) in September of model year 50.

therefore conclude that it is the diapycnal mixing that makes layer 19 (potential density 27.91) lose water. The same situation also holds for layer 18.

Table 3 shows the accumulated contribution from the different components (detrainment, entrainment, convection and diapycnal mixing) in the mass balance of every layer (expressed in terms of global averaged layer thickness) in model year 50. It is seen that layers 2-6 lose water at the rate of about 0.1 m yr^{-1} , and that every component contributes to mass balance, with entrainment and detrainment as the most important processes. Layers 12 and 13, with potential densities of 27.52 and 27.74, get the largest amount of water at the rates of 0.869 m yr^{-1} and 0.851 m yr^{-1} , respectively. Detrainment contributes most to the water gain in layers 12 and 13, whereas diapycnal mixing is a minor factor compared to detrainment. This means that the mixed layer is the main source for forming water with densities consistent with layers 12 and 13.

Based on the figures in Tab. 3, the deep water formation rate is about 9.5 Sv ($\text{Sv}=10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) associated with layer 13, which is in good agreement with the overturning cell (see Sec. 5.10). Of the formation rate of 9.5 Sv (of layer 13), detrainment contributes 7.3 Sv and diapycnal mixing contributes about 2.2 Sv. Layer 15 with potential density 27.74 obtain water at the rate of 0.487 m yr^{-1} corresponding to 5.4 Sv, and the formation of this water mass is mainly due to diapycnal mixing in our experiment. It follows from Tab. 3 that layers 18 and 19 lose mass mainly due to diapycnal mixing.

Note that convection only penetrates into layer 16 in the spin-up integration, and is confined to the GIN Seas in our experiment (see Sec. 5.7). If we compare Tabs. 2 and 3, we find that the rates are in good agreement with each other for layers 12-15, 18 and 19. Note also that layers 20 and 21 lose water only due to diapycnal mixing.

As previously shown in Fig. 13 and Tab. 3, layer 13 (potential density 27.61) shows the largest gain in water, and the water mass increases linearly in time. This increase is mainly due to the large detrainment from the mixed layer in the Irminger and Labrador Basins (see Fig. 33).

Figure 13 shows that layer 15 (potential density 27.74) gets water during the spin-up integration. This increase in water mass partly comes from the detrainment from the mixed layer in GIN Seas (see Fig. 34), but also from diapycnal mixing (see Tab. 3).

Figure 31: Mixed layer entrainment from layer 18 (potential density 27.81) in March of model year 50.

Figure 32: Diapycnal mixing between layer 19 (potential density 27.91) and other isopycnals in model year 50. Positive and negative values denote the gain and lose of water within this layer.

Figure 33: Mixed layer detrainment to layer 13 (potential density 27.61) in April of model year 50.

Figure 34: Mixed layer detrainment to layer 15 (potential density 27.74) in April of model year 50.

	detrainment	entrainment	convection	diapycnal mixing	total effect
mixed layer(m yr ⁻¹)	-195.701	168.479	60.600	-32.855	0.523
layer 02(m yr ⁻¹)	17.318	-20.910	-4.866	8.322	-0.136
layer 03(m yr ⁻¹)	9.110	-12.864	-2.170	5.827	-0.097
layer 04(m yr ⁻¹)	13.432	-15.836	-2.452	4.769	-0.087
layer 05(m yr ⁻¹)	16.933	-17.701	-3.443	4.123	-0.088
layer 06(m yr ⁻¹)	26.285	-18.387	-10.346	2.349	-0.099
layer 07(m yr ⁻¹)	23.266	-15.398	-9.541	1.517	-0.156
layer 08(m yr ⁻¹)	23.547	-13.577	-11.940	1.940	-0.030
layer 09(m yr ⁻¹)	16.358	-12.787	-6.213	2.343	-0.300
layer 10(m yr ⁻¹)	17.251	-15.319	-4.551	2.061	-0.558
layer 11(m yr ⁻¹)	16.877	-14.369	-2.777	0.355	0.086
layer 12(m yr ⁻¹)	7.062	-5.508	-0.969	0.285	0.869
layer 13(m yr ⁻¹)	5.385	-3.683	-1.047	0.197	0.851
layer 14(m yr ⁻¹)	0.812	-0.545	-0.133	0.533	0.667
layer 15(m yr ⁻¹)	0.786	-0.561	-0.099	0.361	0.487
layer 16(m yr ⁻¹)	0.751	-0.589	-0.054	0.028	0.135
layer 17(m yr ⁻¹)	0.529	-0.415	0.000	-0.207	-0.093
layer 18(m yr ⁻¹)	0.000	-0.022	0.000	-1.002	-1.024
layer 19(m yr ⁻¹)	0.000	-0.005	0.000	-0.889	-0.894
layer 20(m yr ⁻¹)	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.035	-0.035
layer 21(m yr ⁻¹)	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.021	-0.021

Table 3: Contribution of different mixing processes in the mass balance of every layer.

5.9 Mixed layer subduction

The properties of the main thermocline are controlled by the annual subduction rate because it is this flux that ventilates the permanent thermocline (Marshall, 1993). The mixed layer has, as previously described, a seasonal cycle in which it deepens in winter and shallows in summer. The water detrained in spring may be re-entrained into the mixed layer in the following winter. However, subduction means that the water which is detrained from the mixed layer remains in the permanent thermocline for a long time (longer compared to the seasonal time scale of the mixed layer). Part of the detrainment in spring re-entrains

into mixed layer in the following winter. Therefore, the subduction is the part of detrainment which escapes the re-entrainment during the following winter. This narrowly defined subduction process determines the rate at which the stratified ocean interior is being “ventilated” (Bleck *et al.*, 1996).

Figure 35 shows the vertical mass flux through the bottom of the mixed layer in model year 50. If the subduction rate is positive, it indicates that total detrainment is greater than total entrainment, meaning that the downward motion is dominant. The largest mass transfer is located in the Irminger Basin and the GIN Seas where large amounts of water detrain into depth to form the deep water masses and the net effect is that the mixed layer “subduct” about 600 m into the permanent thermocline. In the central east Pacific Ocean, upwelling transports water at a rate of about 1000 m yr^{-1} into the mixed layer. In the extratropics, the upwelling is associated with the polarward meridional transport and cyclonic wind stress (positive Ekman pumping in the Northern Hemisphere). Downwelling is related to equatorward meridional transport and anticyclonic wind stress (negative Ekman pumping in the Northern Hemisphere).

Compared with the result of Bleck *et al.* (1996) in which the maximum annual subduction rate is about 1500 m in the Labrador Sea, the subduction rate obtained in this simulation is smaller. This also gives us one reason that the strength of the deep overturning cell in this study (see Sec 5.10) is weaker than that of Bleck *et al.* (1996).

As mentioned before, in the Northern Hemisphere, the mixed-layer thickness reaches its deepest value in March and shallowest value in September. If $\bar{h}$ represents multi-year averaged mixed-layer thickness, $\bar{h}_3$ multi-year averaged mixed-layer thickness in March, and $\bar{h}_9$ multi-year averaged mixed-layer thickness in September. Then we have:

$$\bar{h}_3 = \bar{h} + [entrainment]_{total} \quad (27)$$

$$\bar{h}_9 = \bar{h} - [detrainment]_{total} \quad (28)$$

$$[subduction] = [detrainment]_{total} - [entrainment]_{total} \quad (29)$$

$$[subduction] = 2 * \bar{h} - (\bar{h}_9 + \bar{h}_3) \quad (30)$$

The above defined subduction rate is relative to the base of the annually averaged mixed layer (see Fig. 36). In Irminger and Labrador Basins, the subduction rate is much greater

Figure 35: Subduction rate (m yr⁻¹) relative to the varying base of mixed layer in model year 50.

Figure 36: Subduction rate (m yr⁻¹) relative to the annually averaged base of mixed layer in model year 50.

than that calculated relative to the varying base of the mixed layer. The precise diagnosis of the subduction would require evaluating the strength of the meridional flow in relation to the slope of the late-winter mixed layer interface (Bleck *et al.*, 1996, and Marshall, 1993). New *et al.* (1995) calculated the precisely-defined subduction rate (see appendix A) using an Atlantic Ocean only version of MICOM. Compared with the result of New *et al.* (1995), we conclude that the subduction in the North Atlantic Ocean is positive along the 25°N–45°N line. The subduction reaches the maximum value in the Labrador and the Irminger Basins.

5.10 Meridional circulation in the global ocean

The global conveyor belt connecting the ocean basins is an expression of the thermohaline-driven large-scale meridional circulation. Because of its capacity to transport large amounts of heat and CO_2 , it plays an important role in the climate system (Broecker and Peng, 1992, and Ralf and Rene, 1997). Figures 37 and 38 show the annually averaged meridional and zonal velocity in the global ocean, respectively. The westward equatorial currents and eastward equatorial undercurrent show up clearly in the figures.

Figures 39 and 40 show the annually averaged meridional overturning in the global ocean and the Atlantic Ocean captured by the model. The equation for the meridional overturning volume transport streamfunction ψ can be put in the following form:

$$\psi = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{z(\lambda, \varphi, \rho)}^0 v a \cos \varphi dz d\lambda \quad (31)$$

Here λ and φ are, respectively, longitude and latitude and a is the radius of the earth. In the Atlantic Ocean, the main feature of the circulation is the northward flow of surface water with the southward return flow at depth, representing the “Atlantic Conveyor Belt”. As the surface water flows northward, it becomes denser mainly due to cooling, and at about 60°N, the potential density of surface water matches the values of layers of 13 to 15, and due to hydrostatic instability, deep convection forms the deep water. The deep water passes equator to about 40°S. The large positive cell with strength of 11 Sv near the surface at about 10°N is associated with the maximum meridional heat transport in the Atlantic Ocean (see Fig. 18). The strength of the deep water cell is 11 Sv centered at layer

Figure 37: Annually averaged meridional velocity (cm s^{-1}) in the global ocean.

Figure 38: Annually averaged zonal velocity (cm s^{-1}) in the global ocean.

Figure 39: Annually averaged meridional overturning (S_v) in the global ocean in model year 50. Solid/dashed lines indicate clockwise/counterclockwise rotation looking west.

Figure 40: Annually averaged meridional overturning (S_v) in the Atlantic Ocean in model year 50. Solid/dashed lines indicate clockwise/counterclockwise rotation looking west.

13 (potential density 27.69). In the experiment of Bleck *et al.* (1996), the deep water cell is 17 Sv centered at the layer with potential density 27.74.

The main feature of the meridional circulation in the global ocean is the two strong shallow cells of about 30 Sv in both hemispheres, and the Conveyor Belt. The big shallow cells are associated with the maximum meridional heat transport in the global ocean (see Fig. 17). In the Northern Hemisphere, our result is similar with Hu's result (Hu, 1997), namely, that the deep water appears to return to surface near equator; but different from Bleck's result (Bleck *et al.*, 1996) in which the deep water passes equator and upwells near Antarctica. In the Southern Hemisphere, the model captures the Deacon Cell centered at layer 7 around 48°S which can be described as consisting of northward Ekman transport in the surface layer, sinking to the depths of 1 km or more between 30°S and 45°S, southward flow at these depths, and nearly vertical rising north of 65°S (Bryan, 1991).

Figures 41 and 42 show the meridional overturning in the Atlantic Ocean in January of model year 20 and 50, respectively. The strength of the positive deep water cell during 50°N to 60°N is only 1 Sv in model year 20, but becomes 11 Sv in model year 50. This is also an expression of the evolution of deep water formation in the model.

5.11 Model evolution and deep-water formation in the global ocean

Potential density and thickness of mixed layer in March are showed for every 10 year in Figs. 43- 50. In our experiment, the densest surface water and deepest mixed layer locate in the GIN Seas and the Irminger Basin (potential density reaches 27.83 in Irminger Basin and GIN Seas in March of model year 40 and later on). In late winter, the mixing can penetrate to depths of 1400m in the Irminger Basin and the GIN Seas and deep water is formed by detrainment of mixed layer water. From model year 30 to 50, the thickness of mixed layer in the Irminger Basin gets deeper and deeper (indicates deep water convection). The simulation does not catch the signal of bottom waters with potential density greater than 28.0. According to observation, this water mass should flow across the Greenland-Iceland-Scotland ridge and south of the Denmark Strait (McCartney and Talley, 1982, and

Figure 41: Atlantic Ocean meridional overturning (Sv) in January of model year 20.

Figure 42: Atlantic Ocean meridional overturning (Sv) in January of model year 50.

Dickson *et al.*, 1990). This is possibly due to that the model domain is closed at 72°N . In the Southern Hemisphere, the mixed layer thickness reaches a depth of 1000 m (potential density 27.5) in the Weddell Sea. The reason for the lack of AABW in the simulation is given in Sec. 2.

Deep water with potential density 27.75 (corresponding to layer 15 in our experiment) is thought to be formed in Labrador Sea in the real world (McCartney and Talley, 1982). We show in Figs. 51 - 54 the evolution of thickness of layer 15 in March of model year 30 and 50, and the thickness of layer 13 in April of model year 30 and 50. Temperature of layer 13 in April of model year 30 and 50 is also displayed. From these figures, we can see that the Labrador Sea is a source region of deep water formation (especially, for layer 13). The thickness of layer 13 with potential density 27.69 in the Labrador Basin is about 900 m in April of year 30 and becomes about 1300 m in year 50. Temperature of layer 13 in the Labrador Sea is about 4°C in April of year 30 and becomes about 3°C in year 50. In addition, the Weddell Sea is also a source region of deep water formation. As seen in the figures, the thickness of layer 13 in the Weddell Sea increases from about 200 m in April of year 30 to about 500 m in year 50. The temperature in the Weddell Sea decreases from about 0°C in April of model year 30 to about -1.8°C in year 50. The thickness of layer 15 with potential density 27.74 becomes greater in the North Atlantic Ocean due to both the mixed layer detrainment and diapycnal mixing as mentioned in Sec. 5.8. In the Northern Pacific Ocean, layer 15 also gets water mass due to upwelling caused by diapycnal mixing.

6 Conclusion

This paper has presented the results from a 60-yr spin-up integration experiment with the Miami Isopycnal Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM).

The meridional heat transport is presented and the maximum meridional heat transport occurs around 12°N with a value of about 1.5 PW in the global ocean and around 18°N with a value of 0.75 PW in the Atlantic Ocean. The model also captures the Global Conveyor Belt with the strength of 11 Sv around 56°N for the deep water cell which is somewhat smaller compared with the estimates of 13-14 Sv for the real world (Worthington, 1976).

Figure 43: Mixed layer density in March of model year 30.

Figure 44: Mixed layer thickness in March of model year 30.

Figure 45: Mixed layer density in March of model year 40.

Figure 46: Mixed layer thickness in March of model year 40.

Figure 47: Mixed layer density in March of model year 50.

Figure 48: Mixed layer thickness in March of model year 50.

Figure 49: Mixed layer density in March of model year 60.

Figure 50: Mixed layer thickness in March of model year 60.

Figure 51: Thickness of layer 15 in March of model year 30. (Contour interval is 50 m).

Figure 52: Thickness of layer 15 in March of model year 50. (Contour interval is 50 m).

Figure 53: Thickness of layer 13 in April of model year 30. (Contour interval is 100m).

Figure 54: Thickness of layer 13 in April of model year 50.(Contour interval is 100 m).

Figure 55: Temperature of layer 13 in April of model year 30. (Contour interval is 0.5°C).

Figure 56: Temperature of layer 13 in April of model year 50. (Contour interval is 0.5°C).

We particularly investigate the vertical mass transfer between the isopycnals and mixed layer and conclude that in the lower part of the ocean, diapycnal mixing is important, whereas detrainment and entrainment is important for the upper layers that outcrop into the mixed layer in the seasonal cycle. In the Irminger and Labrador Basins, the mixed layer subducts about 1000 m yr^{-1} into the ocean interior to ventilate the subpolar ocean. In the North Atlantic Ocean, the subtropical gyre is ventilated along and north of the 25°N – 45°N line. In the North Pacific Ocean, the subtropical gyre is ventilated around 36°N . Finally we display the evolution of the modelled deep water formation.

7 Further plans

This study will be continued by adding a thermodynamic-dynamic sea ice model to the present version of MICOM, making the model fully global. The global model will then be integrated for several centuries or more. Quantification of the evolution of the different water masses will follow the discussion given in this thesis, and the analysis will be submitted to an international referee journal.

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A Subduction determination in Marshall (1993)

The instantaneous kinematic subduction rate is defined as the downward velocity of a parcel of fluid relative to the base of the mixed layer (see Marshall, 1993):

$$S = -\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} - \mathbf{u}_b \cdot \nabla h - w_b \quad (32)$$

Here h is the thickness of the mixed layer, $\mathbf{u}_b$ is the horizontal velocity of the particle at the base of the mixed layer, w_b is its vertical velocity, and t is time. In the presence of any discontinuity, $\mathbf{u}_b$ and w_b are taken on the thermocline side of the mixed layer. Over the course of one year, if there is no systematic long-term change in mixed layer characteristics, the temporal term will vanish. We define the annual subduction rate:

$$S_{ann} = -\bar{\mathbf{u}}_H \cdot \nabla H - \bar{w}_H \quad (33)$$

where H is the depth of the mixed layer when it reach its deepest state in winter, the subscript H denotes that the quantity is evaluated at depth H , and overbar represents an annual mean. S_{ann} means total volume transfer per unit horizontal area per year of water cross the slope base of the winter mixed layer to enter the permanent thermocline. On this premise, $-H$ is a fixed surface given by the maximum depth of the wintertime mixed layer at any position. The first term in the preceding equation express the volume flux due to vertical pumping of fluid downward, and the second is the amount which horizontally pass the sloping mixed layer base, namely the lateral induction term. Following Marshall, the vertical velocity at $z = -H$ can be related to Ekman pumping velocity w_{Ek} by applying the linear vorticity balance, and the previous expression then becomes

$$S_{ann} = -\bar{\mathbf{u}}_H \cdot \nabla H - \bar{w}_{Ek} + \frac{\beta}{f} \int_{-H}^0 \bar{v} dz \quad (34)$$

where v is the meridional velocity component, f the Coriolis parameter, and β its meridional gradient. The Ekman pumping increases S_{ann} whereas the meridional transport reduces it.

B Arakawa C grid

Variables distribution on an Arakawa C grid is sketched by Fig. 57.

Figure 57: Spatial distribution of the different variables in the C-grid. Open circles: scalar points, vertical bars: v-momentum points, and horizontal bars: u-momentum points. The frame includes scalar and momentum points with the same i, j indexes.

C Detrainment scheme for the mixed layer.

The ability of the model to support variable T, S fields complicates the mass transfer from the mixed layer to the isopycnic layers, given the need to maintain the reference density in the receiving layer at all times. The solution to this problem as described by Bleck *et al.* (1992) is given below.

Let z_1, T_1, S_1 respectively, be the mixed layer thickness, temperature, and salinity, and let z_k, T_k, S_k be the corresponding quantities in the k_{th} isopycnic layer. Suppose z_1 exceeds the appropriate mixed layer depth which in the Kraus-Turner (1967) model is given by the Monin-Obukhov length L . the goal is to detrain as large a fraction of the excess amount $z_1 - L$ as possible into layer k . Generally, this can not be done without allowing some heat transfer from the detrained water column to the remaining mixed layer. Let ΔT be the largest permissible mixed layer temperature increase resulting from this transfer. (The way of arriving at a plausible ΔT value is to argue that the thermal energy received during

last time step should have been spread over the depth range L rather than z_1 .)

Let z ($\leq z_1 - L$) be the amount of mixed-layer water actually being detrained. Since mixed-layer water is more buoyant than water in layer k , mixing some of the former with the latter generally produces water too light to match the reference density σ_k . We correct this by extracting heat from the mixture, which we add to the remaining column $z_1 - z$ with the intent of raising its temperature to $T_1 + \Delta T$. The unknown in the problem is z . If the heat required to raise T_1 in the column $z_1 - z$ by ΔT is taken out of the column z at the beginning, the water to be detrained is cooled down by the amount $\Delta T(z_1 - z)/z$. Adding this water to layer k produces water of temperature:

$$T_{new} = \frac{(T_1 - \Delta T \frac{z_1 - z}{z}) + T_k z_k}{z + z_k} = \frac{(T_1 + \Delta T)z - \Delta T z_1 + T_k z_k}{z + z_k} \quad (35)$$

and salinity:

$$S_{new} = \frac{S_1 z + S_k z_k}{z + z_k} \quad (36)$$

The T_{new} and S_{new} should satisfy : $\sigma(T_{new}, S_{new}) = \sigma_k$. (E1)

Approximating the equation of state by a third-order polynomial,

$$\sigma(T, S) = c_1 + c_2 T + c_3 S + c_4 T^2 + c_5 T S + c_6 T^3 + c_7 T^2 S, (E2) \quad (37)$$

After some algebraic manipulation that (E1) is satisfied if z is a root of the cubic equation

$$a_3 z^3 + a_2 z^2 + a_1 z + a_0 = 0, (E3) \quad (38)$$

At low temperatures, where (E2) is most nonlinear, (E3) is occasionally found to have more than one possible root; only one of theses, however, usually falls into the range $0 \leq z \leq z_1 - L$. If several roots lie in that range, the largest one is taken. If there is no positive root, no water is being detrained. If the smallest positive exceeds $z_1 - L$, all water below depth L is detrained into layer k , provided the resulting mixed-layer temperature increase (which in this case is known to be less than ΔT) is positive.

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